

Variation of the Electrical Charge of Colloidal Particles. Part IV. The Effect of Dilution on the Charge of Colloidal Particles in the Presence and Absence of Electrolytes.

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The work of Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Rai-Chaudhuri (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 493) on the variation of the charges of arsenious sulphide sols on dilution has been continued in the present paper which also records some interesting observations on ferric hydroxide sol. The conditions for obtaining accurate values for the cataphoretic speed of the particles of ferric hydroxide sol have not been carefully investigated. The question of what constitutes a suitable upper liquid for a particular sol is a problem which must be solved for each sol in a manner indicated in previous papers (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1923, 193A, 102 ; also *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, *loc. cit.*). It seems that simpler modifications of the above method (*cp.* Freundlich and Zeh, *Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1925, **114**, 84 ; Kruyt and Willigen, *Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1927, **130**, 170 ; and *Koll. Zeit.*, 1928, **44**, 22) are not always satisfactory and they should be used after the boundary conditions have been fully investigated.

Discussions as to the conditions of coagulation are always based on certain assumptions as to the electric charge. There are very few observations on these points. The meagre data that are available for or against such assumptions have mostly been obtained by the use of the arrangement of Burton (*Phil. Mag.*, 1906, vi, **11**, 425) or its modifications and they are not reliable as the conditions obtaining at the boundary were not investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Mukherjee's cataphoretic method has been used (*loc. cit.*) in this investigation. Two different U-tubes were used, of which

the one having three side tubes and an effective distance of 3.1 cm. between the side tubes enclosing the boundary for both the upward and downward movements was used for the work with the ferric hydroxide sol and the other had two tubes and an effective distance of 4.2 cm. for both movements and was used for all other measurements. Viscosity corrections have been made and rates of migration have been given in centimeters per second per volt/second multiplied 10^3 times. The temperature of the thermostat was $35^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. In the case of the higher concentrations of the electrolyte the heating effect, on account of the greater conductivity, was tested by placing a milli-ammeter in the circuit of the cataphoretic tube and also by inserting a narrow clinical thermometer inside one of the limbs while the potential between the electrodes was maintained constant. The increase in the current strength on its continued passage for over half an hour could not be detected. The rise in the temperature indicated by the clinical thermometer after half an hour was about 2°F . The consequent change in viscosity is not likely to be more than 2—3%. The boundary remained sharp and flat up to the highest concentrations.

(1) *Ferric Hydroxide Sol.*

Preparation.—Ten c. c. of a saturated solution of ferric chloride were added to 500 c. c. of boiling conductivity water drop by drop with constant stirring and the mixture was then boiled for about 20 minutes. The sol was then cooled and allowed to be dialysed (for about a month and a half) till no trace of iron could be detected in the outer liquid. The dialysis was continued till only a faint trace of chlorine could be detected. It was then stored in clean wide-mouthed Jena glass bottles. In previous measurements of the cataphoretic speed of this sol equiconducting solutions of electrolytes, *e. g.*, potassium chloride (*cp.* Burton, *loc. cit.*) have been used as the upper liquid assuming that this procedure secures a constant potential gradient during the movement. It will be found from what follows that unless the upper liquid procures *the same ionic environment*, as exists in the colloid, the measurements are definitely in error. The ultimate procedure which gave a constant potential gradient and an identical rate for the original sol both for direct and reverse movements was as follows: The sol was coagulated with a few drops of a concentrated solution of K_2SO_4 .

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and the p_H of the supernatant liquid after coagulation was determined colorimetrically. A solution of hydrochloric acid having the same p_H was made equally conducting with the sol by adding to about 500 c. c. of this solution the requisite quantity (a few drops) of the saturated ferric chloride solution, used in the preparation of the sol so that the volume of the dilute hydrochloric acid solution did not change materially. This solution was found satisfactory as the upper liquid. It has been however found that a hydrochloric acid solution having slightly higher p_H is more satisfactory probably because of the fact that on the addition of the small volume of concentrated ferric chloride solution the p_H becomes lower. The results are given below. The p_H values given in Tables I—III refer to the supernatant liquid after coagulation as described above.

TABLE I.

Pure Sol A ; p_H 3.2 ; 0.042 moles of Fe_2O_3 per litre.

Upper liquid.	Upward.			Downward.		
	Potential gradient.		Rate of migration.	Potential gradient.		Rate of migration.
	Before.	After.		Before.	After.	
KCl	0.661	0.647	29.2	0.573	0.900	87.2
LiCl	0.709	0.707	16.8	0.688	0.860	88.0
KCl in .001N-HCl	0.678	0.694	26.6	0.662	0.878	50.8
HCl	0.552	0.775	46.4	0.767	0.460	44.0

TABLE II.

Pure Sol B ; p_H 2.9 ; 0.0342 moles of Fe_2O_3 per litre.

Upper liquid.	Upward.			Downward.		
	Potential gradient.		Rate of migration.	Potential gradient.		Rate of migration.
	Before.	After.		Before.	After.	
HCl	0.647	0.817	56.5	0.796	0.682	50.2
LiCl in .001N-HCl	0.765	0.790	37.7	0.737	0.859	52.8
LiCl	0.590	0.586	32.5	0.586	0.776	63.6
$FeCl_2$ in .001N-HCl	0.707	0.764	44.2	0.778	0.704	47.4
$FeCl_2$ in .00067N-HCl	0.671	0.671	58.4	0.675	0.673	49.5

TABLE III.

Sol B at different dilutions.

Dilution. Volume of sol : Volume of water.	Resistance in ohms in the same cell.	pH of upper liquid after coag.	Upward.		Rate of migration.	Downward.		Depression of boundary in 20 min.	
			Potential gradient.			Potential gradient.			
			Before.	After.		Before.	After.		
Sol B	192	2.9	0.671	0.671	53.4	0.675	0.673	49.5	Nil
1:1	542	3.7	0.688	0.688	54.5	0.698	0.688	51.7	Nil
1:3	932	4.5	0.694	0.708	52.9	0.708	0.677	57.4	Nil
1:5	1304	4.7	0.679	0.676	54.1	0.676	0.672	72.1	29 cm. taken before expt.
1:10	2540	5.4	0.771	0.773	46.4	0.777	0.773	81.7	15 cm. taken after expt.
1:20	3250	5.6	0.758	0.780	48.7	0.786	0.767	80.7	28 cm. in 10 min. before expt.

TABLE IV (Fig. I).

Dilution.	B	B/2	B/3	B/5	B/10	B/20
Mean rate of migration.	51.5	53.1	55.1	63.1	64.1	64.7

It will be seen from Tables I and II that the potential gradient does not at all remain constant during cataphoresis in both directions except when the mixture of ferric chloride and hydrochloric acid prepared as stated above is used as the upper liquid. The other electrolytes also show a great difference in the values of the direct and reverse movements. Hydrochloric acid alone secures a steadier potential gradient but the difference between the movements in opposite directions is still marked. That this difference does not result from the speed or free fall of the particles would be apparent from column X, Table III. The constancy in the cataphoretic speed when the rate of free fall is negligible and of the potential gradient for movements in both directions indicates that the particles are moving in a 'uniform ionic environment' (cp. a paper by one of us on the theory of cataphoretic measurements to be published in the Journal of the Indian Chemical Society).

We find from Table II that the rate of downward movement of the sol at higher dilutions is considerably greater than that of the upward movement even when the condition of steady potential gradient has been attained and that the particles have a rate of settling comparable to the cataphoretic speed. It appears that the rate of settling on account of gravity during cataphoresis is difficult to measure. Different values are obtained according as the rate is measured after the boundary rises to the level necessary for the measurement and before the cataphoresis begins or after the cataphoresis has stopped. Similar observations have been previously recorded with gold sols in Part II of this series. The value given in the last column in Table III, however, shows that the rate of free fall is considerable and is observable only at higher dilution beginning from 1:5. The mean of the two movements in the up and down directions should give the correct cataphoretic speed as the rates of settling vary in the same manner for both movements. The mean cataphoretic speeds given in Table IV show this as we get a constant speed after a certain dilution. Table IV shows that the cataphoretic speed increases on dilution and becomes constant at higher dilutions. The sols A and B have a fairly high concentration of free acid and it is probable that the amount of ferric ions adsorbed by the particles does not alter to any marked extent on dilution. This can be expected if we remember that the reaction between ferric hydroxide molecules on the surface and hydrogen ion is chemical. On diluting the sol the chlorine ion concentration decreases which thereby decreases the electrical adsorption of chlorine ions on the surface so that the density of the charge increases. It is difficult to reconcile the observed increase in cataphoretic speed with the lower coagulating concentration of ferric hydroxide sol on dilution which has been previously observed by several authors. This question will form the subject matter of a separate paper.

On keeping the U-tube filled with the colloid and a pure solution of lithium chloride as upper liquid overnight it was found that the upper liquid becomes faintly yellowish brown but this liquid did not show any marked Tyndall effect when examined by light from an ordinary lamp. This observation shows that the colloid contains a trace of free ferric ions which diffuse into the upper layer. On the other hand the upper liquid prepared by mixing hydrochloric acid and ferric chloride as described above, though it appears colourless to the naked eye when freshly prepared (it also remains colourless during

the measurement), becomes coloured on keeping overnight. It is likely that the concentration of free ferric ions in the colloid is lower than that in the upper liquid we have used.

The observations made above lead to the conclusion that there are some free H⁺ ions and Cl⁻ ions in the sol itself possibly also some free Fe⁺⁺⁺ ions in addition to the charged colloidal particles. For any precise statement however we must know the accurate composition of the sol itself and await further investigation.

(2) *Arsenious Sulphide Sol.*

A saturated solution of arsenious oxide was mixed with twice its volume of conductivity water. One litre of the diluted solution was added to a litre of conductivity water saturated with hydrogen sulphide, a thin stream of which was continued till a trace of arsenious acid was left free in the solution (*cp.* Mukherjee and Choudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 296). The sol contained about 16 milli-moles of arsenious trisulphide per litre.

For upper liquid in this sol an equally conducting hydrochloric acid solution was used (*cp.* Mukherjee, *loc. cit.*)

TABLE V.

Arsenious Sulphide Sol A.

Dilution. Volume of pure sol : Volume of water.	Rate of migration.		
	Direct.	Reverse	Mean (corrected for viscosity).
Pure	73.9	70.6	74.1
1:1	67.4	65.0	65.8
1:5	62.3	55.4	58.3
1:10	49.2	45.5	46.3

TABLE VI.

Sol A diluted 1:1.

Conc. of potassium chloride in normality.	Rate of migration.		
	Direct.	Reverse.	Mean.
0	67.4	65.0	65.8
0.001	55.1	54.38	54.7
0.01	54.7	52.5	53.6
0.05	65.5	59.6	62.6
0.056	66.7	65.9	66.3
0.056*	67.8	69.7	68.8

TABLE VII.

Sol A diluted 1:5

Conc. of potassium chloride in normality.	Rate of migration.		
	Direct.	Reverse.	Mean.
0	62.3	55.4	58.4
0.001	49.8	46.3	48.1
0.01	51.5	50.1	50.8
0.05	58.6	57.9	58.3
0.067	60.3	62.6	61.5
0.067*	50.6	50.5	50.6

* After coagulation.

TABLE VIII.

Sol A diluted 1 : 10.

Conc. of potassium chloride in normality.	Rate of migration.		
	Direct.	Reverse.	Mean.
0	49.2	45.5	46.3
0.001	50.3	45.0	48.2
0.01	53.0	52.7	52.9
0.05	64.7	59.2	61.9
0.067	75.2	69.8	72.5
0.071	67.7	66.6	67.2
0.077	68.1†	47.3*	—

The results for zero concentration of electrolyte in Table IV are shown graphically in Fig. I. The variations of charge with different

FIG. I.

† The sol coagulated during the measurement.

* After coagulation.

concentrations of potassium chloride at different dilutions of sol as given in Tables VI, VII and VIII are plotted graphically in Fig. II in Curves 1, 2, 3 respectively.

FIG. II.

DISCUSSION.

(a) General.

The only reliable measurements of the cataphoretic speed of colloidal arsenious sulphide particles in presence of potassium chloride apart from those published from this laboratory are those of Freundlich and Zeh (*loc. cit.*) who took cognisance of the improvements suggested by Mukherjee (*loc. cit.*). They observed a gradual decrease in the cataphoretic speed with increase in concentration up to a concentration of 0.01N (*loc. cit.*, p. 84). They, however, consider their measurement at concentrations higher than 0.02N to be uncertain (*vide* foot-note, p. 84). Their values are given in Curve 4, Fig. II. Curve 5 has been plotted from the data of Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Rai-Chaudhuri (*loc. cit.*). Mr. S. G. Chaudhury in this laboratory observed in 1925 that with a particular sample of arsenious sulphide sol potassium chloride showed a peculiar behaviour of a decrease in charge at low concentrations followed by a rise at

higher concentrations. But lithium chloride and hydrochloric acid did not show this peculiarity up to the concentration studied (.005N and .01N respectively). It was thought desirable to confirm this observation fully before publication. His data are now given in Curve 6, Fig. II. Since then Kruyt and Willigen (*loc. cit.*) have recorded a continuous increase in the charge with increasing concentrations of potassium chloride as shown in Curve 7, Fig. II. It is obvious that the run of the curves depends on the quality of the sol. The measurements of Freundlich and Zeh (*loc. cit.*) were not made at 35°. They took measurements at 20°. The temperature at which Kruyt and Willigen worked is however not given in their paper.* From Freundlich and Zeh's figure one can calculate the values of the cataphoretic speed at 35° assuming that the mobility varies inversely as the viscosity of water. It is not claimed that these corrected values represent the actual values at that temperature and they are given in Curve 8 only for the sake of comparison. In Part II of this series of papers a slight initial decrease followed by a rise was observed with sodium citrate and potassium ferrocyanide. These observations show that the influence of an electrolyte on the cataphoretic speed is much more complex than has hitherto been supposed to be the case and that the quality of the sol determines this behaviour. As to the actual factors which are responsible for this difference, it is not possible to say anything definite pending further investigations. The theoretical considerations set forth by one of us (*Trans. Far. Soc.*, 1921, 16, 103; *Phil. Mag.*, 1922, 44, 321; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 191) and the experimental work in this laboratory enable us to give a plausible physical picture. Before proceeding to consider this tentative explanation, it is necessary to discuss two aspects of Curves 1—3.

(a) *Cataphoretic Speed and Coagulating Concentration.*

Kruyt and Willigen (*loc. cit.*) found no diminution in the rate of migration up to the highest concentration (.066N) they used but their observations did not extend to the coagulating concentration (.08N). They assume that at the coagulating concentration the

* In a later paper they mention that their measurements were taken at 20°. Curve 9 has been plotted from their data after correcting for the lower viscosity at 35°.

cataphoretic speed is much greater than that of the pure sol and attempts to explain it on the ground that the dielectric constant of the medium increases at these high electrolytic concentrations to such an extent that the potential of the double layer is really smaller in spite of the increase in cataphoretic speed. They conclude that coagulation takes place at a critical potential as postulated by Powis and state, "Diese Kataphoretischen Messungen widersprechen deshalb nicht notwendig Powis'sche Theorie des kritischen Potentials (p. 176)." Excepting the measurement of Powis (*Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1915, 89, 186) by Burton's method (*loc.cit.*) which certainly gives erroneous results in the case of arsenious sulphide sols, there are no measurements of cataphoretic speed extending to the coagulating concentration. In Curves 1, 2, and 3 we have the first reliable evidence that coagulation actually takes place at a much higher cataphoretic speed than that for the "pure" sol. It may also be remarked that we do not measure the potential directly but we calculate it from the cataphoretic speed. Working on arsenious sulphide sols Rai-Choudhuri and others (*loc. cit.*) have shown that with some electrolytes coagulation does not occur even when the cataphoretic speed is as low as 9, though with some other electrolytes coagulation occurs at a cataphoretic speed of about 43. They pointed out that "the stability is not so directly related to the charge as is generally believed to be the case. Thus the electrolytes with divalent cations depress the charge enormously. We have stable sols with these electrolytes where the particles show a rate of migration ranging from 20 to as low as 9 (calcium benzoate). From the slope of the curve with potassium, sodium or lithium chloride as the added electrolyte, it would appear that coagulation takes place before a velocity of about 20 has been reached. We would particularly refer to the low charge with calcium benzoate (pp. 513-14)." It has also been observed (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 296) that at the same hydrogen ion concentration the cataphoretic speed is always greater for hydrochloric acid than for acetic acid though the former has an incomparably greater coagulating power. *It is evident therefore that the current belief regarding the existence of a critical potential characteristic of the coagulating concentration of different-electrolytes for a given sample of a colloid is erroneous.*

An explanation of the non-existence of a critical cataphoretic speed has been given by one of us in previous papers (*loc. cit.*, also

previous papers). In these discussions it has been assumed that the cataphoretic speed is a measure of the density of the charge on the surface. This assumption is in conformity with Lamb's equation*:

$$e.H = \bar{\beta}.u \dots \dots \dots (1).$$

where u is the rate of migration per sec. per volt/cm., e the surface density of charge, H the potential gradient and $\bar{\beta}$ represents the facility of slip which is assumed to depend only on the viscosity.

On the basis of Heilmholtz's* treatment in its usual form we have

$$u_0 = u.\eta = \frac{k\phi}{4\pi} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

where u is the observed cataphoretic speed per sec. per volt/cm., η is the coefficient of viscosity, k is the dielectric constant of the medium in the double layer and ϕ is the potential of the double layer. The potential is usually calculated from the surface density of charge on the colloidal particle, the thickness of the double layer and the dielectric constant of the medium as in the case of electrostatic charges on two concentric spherical surfaces. In that event the assumed proportionality between the density of the charge and the cataphoretic speed would imply that either the thickness of the double layer is constant or that it is a suitable function of the surface density such that the product of the thickness of the surface density increases or decreases, as the surface density increases or decreases. The analytical measurements on the adsorption of ions by colloid surfaces (charged surfaces) when compared to cataphoretic and endosmotic measurements under similar conditions strongly point at a direct relationship between the density of charge and the cataphoretic or endosmotic movements. The relationship between the adsorption of coagulating ions, and the coagulating concentration also supports it. Krutz and Willigen (*loc. cit.*) remark (p. 173): "Es muss also irgendein Fehler vorliegen in der Theorie welche Parallelismus zwischen kataphoretische Geschwindigkeit und Ladung voraussetzt." If the cataphoretic speed is expressed in terms of the surface density of the charge the dielectric constant does not appear

* Graetz, "Handbuch der Elektrizität und Magnetismus," 1921, Vol. II, pp. 366-428.

in the equation of cataphoretic speed unless one assumes that the thickness of the double layer is proportional to the dielectric constant. While such a relationship may appear probable on theoretical grounds* it does not help us in the present discussion, as it has been observed by A. Nagaraja Rao in this laboratory that curves of similar form are obtained if one uses a dilute (up to 10 per cent.) alcoholic solution of potassium chloride. It would thus appear that a much more detailed theoretical treatment than is customary is required, for variations in dielectric constant as suggested by Kruyt cannot account for the shape of Curves 1, 2 and 3. We find from Fig. II that the run of Curve 5, which gives the measurements recorded in our previous paper, agrees with Freundlich's (Curve 4) and that they conform to the usual assumption that coagulation takes place at a lower cataphoretic speed. All the other curves differ in this respect from these two curves. It is therefore interesting to know that the sol used in the previous paper was prepared in the manner usually described in papers from Freundlich's laboratory as follows:—"A saturated solution of arsenious oxide was mixed with twice its volume of conductivity water and the resulting solution was added to an equal volume of the water saturated with hydrogen sulphide which was then passed through the solution until all the arsenic had been transformed into arsenious sulphide. This took about one hour and a half. Then a current of hydrogen was passed till the sol was perfectly free from hydrogen sulphide. The sol was kept in Jena glass bottles wrapped up with black paper in a dark place but as care was not taken to have arsenious acid in excess polythionic ions may be present. The sols contained about 16 millimoles of arsenious trisulphide per litre." (*loc. cit.*, p. 497). Choudhury and Kundu, (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 345) have shown that the particles of the sol prepared in this manner have got a chemical composition different from those of the sols used in this investigation in which care has been taken to stop the stream of hydrogen sulphide in time to leave an excess of free arsenious acid. To this difference in chemical composition should be referred the decrease in the cataphoretic speed at high concentration of electrolyte generally observed by Choudhury and others. A comparison of Curves 3 and 9 in Fig. II also shows that they have more or less the same form

* There are other possibilities which will form the subject of a separate communication.

and refer to two sols which have the lowest initial cataphoretic speed. *The increase in dielectric constant at high concentrations is a necessary assumption in order to explain the difficulty that coagulation takes place at a much higher cataphoretic speed. But it does not seem to be a sufficient explanation.* We have also to account for the great difference in the shapes of curves and as the electrolyte and its concentrations are common factors we have also to assume the existence of specific factors. As mentioned already small additions of alcohol bring out more strongly the peculiar shape of these curves.

(b) *The Mechanism of Coagulation.*

The most interesting peculiarity of Curves 2 and 3 is the change in speed after coagulation showing that some irreversible change has set in after coagulation (Mukherjee and Mazumdar, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 785). This decrease in the cataphoretic speed is not due to the settling of the coagulum as the direct and reverse movements agree. Here also the effect depends on the quality of the sol. The dilute sols show this effect and the original sol does not show it. The coagulating concentrations of arsenious sulphide sols on dilutions do not show any such complicated behaviour as the cataphoretic speeds in Curves 1, 2 and 3. Mention may be made in this connection that addition of non-electrolytes, or weak or organic acids (Chaudhury and others, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 253-55) does not in several instances alter the coagulating concentration in the least. These considerations make it plausible that the nature of the coagulating ion determines to a large extent its coagulating concentration. Probably two particles where they touch each other after performing the electrical work referred to above can form a stable aggregate only when they have simultaneously entrained in the surface of contact an equivalent amount of the oppositely charged ion. Such a condition necessarily limits the percentage of successful collisions and make it dependent on the kinetics of the ionic interchange between the double layer and the bulk of the liquid. The concentration of the coagulating ion, its valency and its mobility will be factors affecting the process. This idea is similar to that of Whetham with this difference that the electric work mentioned above comes in as an additional factor. Where coagulation takes place at low concentration of electrolytes, *e.g.*, those having polyvalent coagulating ions the electrical work is probably the

determining factor. At high concentration of electrolytes it is possible that the facilities for entrainment are the more important.

The Cataphoretic Speed and Adsorption of Ions.

Regarding the variation of the cataphoretic speed with the concentration of the electrolyte we shall proceed on the basis that the cataphoretic speed is proportional to the density of charge on the surface. As stated before Curves 5 and 4 (or 8) refer to sols which contain a greater percentage of sulphur than that indicated by the formula As_2S_3 . The surfaces of the colloidal particles of these two sols are probably fully covered by hydrosulphides (these sols smell of hydrogen sulphide on keeping) and the anion adsorption is weak for these sols (compare *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 794). Consequently we get a continual decrease in cataphoretic speed with increasing concentration of electrolytes (*vide* Curves 4 or 8 and 5). It would be interesting to find what happens at still higher concentrations. The greater effect of divalent cations (*vide infra*) would indicate their greater adsorbability but coagulation takes place at a lower cataphoretic speed on account of the low concentration of the cation and the consequent smaller probability of entrainment of ions.

The sol prepared by the other method contains a smaller proportion of sulphur and an excess of arsenious oxide. It has also a higher charge. We would imagine that the surface of these particles contain a much smaller amount of hydrogen sulphide in a state of adsorption on account of the excess of arsenious oxide and the corresponding smaller concentration of hydrogen sulphide in the bulk of the liquid. For the same reason probably divalent sulphidions instead of hydrosulphidions are present on the surface so that the surface density of the charge is greater. The surface should in that event contain a larger number of places available for the adsorption of anions. So long as the density of the surface charge remains high in view of the divalent nature of the sulphidions and the electrical repulsion against chloridions the adsorption of potassium ions predominates. As the charge decreases the adsorbability of the potassium ion becomes progressively weaker and that of the chloridions greater and ultimately predominates over the former. One would expect that when the surface has been nearly saturated with chloridions the adsorption of the potassium ion would again predominate and a decrease in the charge would be noticeable. There is

evidence for this statement in Curve 3. As dilution proceeds the initial charge diminishes indicating a smaller number of sulphidions and a greater capacity to adsorb chloridions. When the initial charge is sufficiently low as in Curves 3 and 7 (or 9) the adsorption of chloridions predominates from the beginning. Coagulation takes place at higher cataphoretic speed probably as the result of a balance between the opposite effects of the higher dielectric constant pointed out by Kruyt and of the increased facilities for the entrainment of oppositely charged ions. The increase in the dielectric constant if fully established would also explain the fact that coagulation takes place at a higher cataphoretic speed when the coagulating ion is univalent which has been observed with the other type of the sol. The great drop in cataphoretic speed on coagulation may be imagined to result from irreversible aggregation when the particles form common surfaces and the neighbouring molecules suffer a rearrangement passing on to a more regular arrangement in conformity with its crystalline character so that the primarily adsorbed anions and their partner cations are loosened from the surface and a diminution in the density of the charge on the surface takes place. Such a state of affairs appears to be plausible in the light of the observations of Freundlich ("Kapillarchemie," 1922, pp. 622-632; *cp.* specially Freundlich and Schucht, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1913, 85, 660). The following remarks of Freundlich are quoted below :

"Es ist auch, wie Zsigmondy (*Nachr. D. K. Gotting Gesellsch. d. Wissensch.*, 1917, S. 33) mit Recht bemerkt, nicht notwendig, dass die Einzelteilchen in diesen frisch koagulierten Flocken unmittelbar aneinander haften müssten ; sie können sehr wohl noch durch ultramikroskopische Flüssigkeitshäute getrennt sein. * * * Auch jetzt wird die vorhandene Ladung eine Abstossung bedingen, die um so grösser ist, je grösser diese Ladung, und nur die Teilchen die bei ihren Schwingungen mit einer gewissen kritischen Wucht zusammenstossen, werden sich unmittelbar berühren, inniger vereinigen und verschmelzen. Die erforderliche kritische Wucht ist um so kleiner, je geringer die Ladung, je grösser die Koagulatorkonzentration ist voraus-gesetzt, dass noch keine Umladung jenseits des isoelektrischen Punktes stattgefunden hat. Je grösser die Koagulatorkonzentration ist, und je kleiner damit die Ladung, um so grösser also auch die Zahl der Teilchen, die die nötige Wucht haben, um so grösser also auch die Geschwindigkeit des Vergrösserns und des Adsorptionsrückganges. * * * * *

Diese Theorie vernachlässigt, vielleicht zu Unrecht, den Umstand, dass die Flocken bei verschiedener Koagulatorkonzentration wahrscheinlich eine verschieden grosse Anzahl von Primärteilchen enthalten."

We find that of the three sols this drop is observed for the two with a smaller initial charge. From the above discussion it will appear that these two sols will contain a greater ratio of primarily adsorbed chlorine ions to sulphide ions and the rearrangement of the molecules referred to above is more likely to affect the adsorptive power of the surface for the chloridions whose adsorption is weaker than that of the sulphide ions. The explanation given above has obviously its limitations but is put forward as a basis for further work.

The difference between the two type of sols regarding their capacity to adsorb chlorine ions may explain the varying stress laid by different authors on the effect of the anion on the coagulating capacity of cations so far as arsenious sulphide sols are concerned (Weiser, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1921, 25, 680; Dhar and Ghosh, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, 31, 187).

